

TOPIC "ISSUES OF IMPROVING ADMINISTRATIVE AND LEGAL SUPPORT FOR THE PROTECTION OF CITIZENS' RIGHTS IN THE SPHERE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY"

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ABSTRACT

Administrative-legal methods for ensuring the protection of citizens' rights in the field of entrepreneurial activity in Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan; foreign experience in protecting entrepreneurs' rights: institutions, mechanisms, and development directions have been studied. Proposals and recommendations were also voiced to improve the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan regulating the administrative and legal procedure for implementing and protecting citizens' rights in the field of entrepreneurial activity.

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The protection of rights is interpreted from the perspective of legal theory as a complex socio-legal activity aimed at restoring a violated right, suppressing offenses, and ensuring legal stability through the application of mandatory state measures.

Administrative-legal methods for protecting rights in the field of entrepreneurship were studied, primarily the jurisdictional forms involving state bodies, specifically the Ministry of Justice, the Business Ombudsman, the prosecutor's office, and judicial bodies. The non-jurisdictional form includes the entrepreneur's ability to independently protect their rights and resist legal pressure through the public and mass media.

The main administrative-legal methods for protecting the rights of business entities include the system of state control and monitoring; the mechanism for imposing administrative liability; and the institution of reviewing complaints through administrative procedures.

Appeals regarding the protection of entrepreneurs' rights in the Republic of Karakalpakstan: In recent years, out of 514 appeals received by the Business Ombudsman,

179 were satisfied, 209 received clarifications, and 92 were rejected. This testifies not only to the effective operation of the current system but also to the presence of certain shortcomings in law enforcement practice.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, an institutional and regulatory system for protecting rights in the field of entrepreneurial activity has been established, which is intended to contribute to guaranteeing the economic freedoms of citizens, reducing administrative pressure, and ensuring the stability of the business environment. Relevance: the need to increase legal literacy, increase transparency, and ensure uniform law enforcement practice.

In recent years, institutional reforms in the field of business protection have intensified in Uzbekistan. Especially in this direction, there is an expansion of the activities of special human rights and control institutions. Specifically, the central link of this system is the institution of the Authorized Person under the President for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities (Business Ombudsman), and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Office of the Authorized Person under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities, which is a pre-trial form of administrative-legal protection. In total, between 2020 and 2024, 2,993 appeals were received by the Office, of which 1,506 received explanations, 1,499 were satisfied, and in 88 cases, lawsuits were filed in court. Analysis shows that in 2021-2022, the number of appeals increased by 28.9 percent, which is explained by the growth of economic activity and legal awareness following the pandemic.

However, the reduction in the number of appeals by 39.7 percent in 2023-2024 is explained by two main factors: strengthening the preventive control system, that is, increasing the effectiveness of measures aimed at preventing offenses; Reducing administrative barriers as a result of implementing digital control through the "Permit" and "License" information systems.

At the same time, the reduction in the number of lawsuits by 70.6 percent (from 34 in 2021 to 10 in 2024) indicates an increase in administrative-procedural efficiency. In other words, most disputes between business entities are now resolved through the Business Ombudsman.

In January-September 2025, 7,175 appeals were received by the Business Ombudsman of the Republic of Uzbekistan, indicating the high demand of entrepreneurs for a legal protection system. According to the information, 28 percent of appeals relate to the tax sphere, 12 percent to decisions of state bodies and illegal actions of officials, 10 percent to land and cadastral issues, and 9 percent to banking and credit problems. These figures prove that problems in the tax and financial spheres remain the most serious obstacle to entrepreneurial freedom. Therefore, the necessity of reforming tax administration through simplification, increased transparency, and digitalization has been substantiated.

Analyzing the legislation and practice of foreign countries in the field of protecting entrepreneurs' rights (specifically Germany, Great Britain, the USA, Japan, and Russia), it was established that one of the priority areas of their state policy is the support of entrepreneurship.

Based on comparative analysis, the following aspects of entrepreneurs' rights protection mechanisms in foreign countries differ from Uzbekistan: the level of institutional

independence—the business ombudsman and regulatory bodies in Germany and the USA operate independently of the executive branch, while in Uzbekistan this institution operates under the President; the effectiveness of judicial protection—administrative courts operate actively in Germany and Russia, while in Uzbekistan this system is being gradually formed; and preventive mechanisms that prevent violations of entrepreneurial rights abroad, whereas in our country this system is only just beginning to develop.

At the same time, the state is successfully implementing advanced aspects of foreign experience (Ombudsman institution, simplified control system, electronic licensing, digitalization of public services) into national practice.

As institutional and legal foundations for supporting entrepreneurship in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, it should be noted that the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2022, No. PP-264 "On additional measures to develop entrepreneurship in the northern districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan," the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 8, 2023, No. UP-129 "On additional measures to create favorable conditions for entrepreneurs in the Republic of Karakalpakstan," and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 14, 2025, No. PP-248 "On further accelerating measures for the socio-economic development of the Republic of Karakalpakstan" are aimed at reducing territorial disparities, developing healthy competition and ensuring sustainable socio-economic growth, eliminating unnecessary bureaucratic barriers, strengthening the legal protection of business, and increasing economic activity in the regions.

The example of the Republic of Karakalpakstan shows that special legal and economic procedures, tax and credit benefits, and measures to support women's and youth entrepreneurship aimed at regional development contribute to increasing the number and activity of business entities. At the same time, an important condition for strengthening the legal guarantees of entrepreneurial activity is the reduction of state control and the need to increase the efficiency of the administrative complaints system.

In the field of ensuring the activities of executive authorities in exercising and protecting the rights of business entities, it is advisable to implement artificial intelligence in the following areas: developing information systems that ensure the implementation of their competence tasks; evaluating the effectiveness of activities; and monitoring the execution of instructions.

It was noted that the system of territorial economic preferences introduced in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is not only a factor of socio-economic growth but also a territorial innovative model of public administration. It is scientifically substantiated as a successful synthesis of the principles of "territorial differentiation" and "flexible fiscal policy" in the practice of administrative-legal regulation.

This experience can serve as an important scientific and practical basis for ensuring regional economic equality and forming a sustainable entrepreneurial infrastructure on a national scale.

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